

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF THROUGH-THE-THICKNESS STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN TRANSVERSE CRACK TENSION TEST SAMPLES

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ABSTRACT

Transverse Crack Tension (TCT) samples represent an alternative to End Notched Flexure configurations for the characterization of pure mode II fracture toughness of Fibre Reinforced Polymer composites. TCT is supposed to reproduce a pure Mode II failure mechanism while avoiding the frictional energy dissipation between the flanks of a starter crack. The TCT geometry is that of a unidirectional tensile sample where a number of embedded plies, centered on the middle plane, are cut in the transverse fibres direction. The tensile loading should then activate four symmetric fronts of mode II delamination from the transverse cut tips. The present work describes the implementation of two full field experimental stress analysis techniques: Thermoelastic Stress Analysis (TSA) and a Digital Image Correlation (DIC). These are applied to evaluate the stresses and strains on the through-the-thickness surface of a TCT sample during static and cyclic loading. The stress and strain information carried out by the thermoelastic signal and DIC analysis are analyzed to investigate the effectiveness of the TCT specimen for the purposes of Mode II characterization.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Transverse Crack Tension (TCT) test is widely used in the aeronautic industry for the characterization of pure mode II fracture delamination. The test consists of a unidirectional laminate loaded along the fibers direction, with a certain number of embedded cut laminas across the middle plane (see Figure 1). Once the critical conditions are reached, delamination propagates from the artificial crack tips, i.e. at the interface between the cut and the continuous plies. Such conditions determine a critical remote stress for the evaluation of the mode II fracture toughness [1]. Wisnom [2] and Cui et al. [3] have reported the existence of a size effect on the fracture toughness measured from TCT samples under quasi-static loading. In particular they observed that sample thickness and the ratio between cut and uncut plies determined some differences in the initial fracture toughness, and affected the stability of delamination propagation. Such reported size effects are in contrast with the classical assumption of delamination fracture toughness being an intrinsic property of the material. In [3] it was also suggested that modifications of fracture toughness were a consequence of the arising of transverse compressive

stresses, whose intensity is related to the thickness of the TCT sample. Van der Meer and Sluys [1] proposed a material model able to account for shear non-linearity and for the influence of frictional effects on mode II crack delamination activated by transverse compressive stresses, which was able to simulate some of the reported size effects.

To the authors knowledge there is no work available on the experimental evaluation of the stress field on the through-thickness face of a TCT sample. It is believed that such evaluation could provide some useful insights, such as detecting the presence and extent of transverse stresses influencing the delamination onset.

Figure 1: TCT sample scheme

In this work an initial experimental campaign evidenced several difficulties in performing the TCT test and in post-processing data. In particular, samples with small thickness did not delaminate, due to the material reaching its ultimate tensile stress before the conditions for mode II delamination. With thicker samples, the residual stiffness after initial crack propagation was usually comparable to the one before crack nucleation, making it difficult to visualize a univocal critical load for data reduction. Moreover direct observation of the crack onset revealed that delamination seldom started at the same time in the four directions from the transverse cut tips. This is probably due to the lack of perfect symmetry idealized by the analytical model. This behavior determines a further modification of the stress distribution, and adds uncertainty to the amount of critical energy needed to start a delamination. One example of non-symmetrical configuration was, for instance, observed with the testing of samples manufactured by vacuum bagging. These samples presented a small local variation of thickness in the zone with the cut plies, which very likely influenced the critical delamination conditions.

The present work proposes the implementation of two full-field experimental stress analysis techniques to evaluate the strain and stress field on the through-thickness surface of TCT samples. The first technique consisted of a 2D Digital Image Correlation set up running during a quasi-static loading to failure. The second technique is a Thermoelastic Stress Analysis performed on the TCT samples under cyclic loading within the elastic regime. Both techniques have allowed to highlight some interesting features of the stress field, useful to better interpret the behavior of the TCT sample.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and specimens geometry

Two CFRP materials have been prepared and tested. The first used unidirectional Hexcel IM7-8552 prepregs, cured in a hot press according to the supplier's specifications [4]. Three unidirectional laminates were in particular prepared: $[0_n/0_{2n_cut}/0_n]$ with $n=3, 6,$ and 9 , obtaining a single layer thickness of 0.125 mm and a total laminate thickness of respectively: 1.5 mm, 3 mm and 4.5 mm. Samples were then cut with areal dimensions of 20×300 mm².

The second material was prepared by using a dry fabric, impregnated by hand lay-up and consolidated in a vacuum bag during room temperature curing. The dry carbon fibres consisted of a unidirectional low-crimped fabric, with primary warp fibres held together by fine strips woven in the weft direction. The fabric had an areal weight of 300 g/m². The matrix resin was an epoxy SX8Evo supplied by Mates Italiana srl, able to cure at room temperature conditions after 24 hours, achieving a final Tg of about 90 °C. A unidirectional laminate was manufactured with lay-up $[0_9/0_{18_cut}/0_9]$, and final thickness of 9.5 mm. Cut tensile samples had dimensions of 7.5×250 mm². It is in particular reported that the vacuum bag samples presented a slightly

indented area on the side of the face resting against the bag and above the zone of the transverse cut.

2.2 Digital Image Correlation

Digital image correlation methods are based on the evaluation of the distortions related to the gray level of each pixel, or set of pixels, and the correlation is calculated for sets of pixels where the displacement is assumed to be homogeneous [5][6]. If $f(x,y)$ indicates the function related to the gray level of the pixels of the undeformed image and $f^*(x^*,y^*)$ the one related to the image after distortion, it is possible to write:

$$f^*(x^*, y^*) - f(x + u(x, y), y + v(x, y)) = 0 \quad (1)$$

that represents the theoretical relationship between two discrete functions, with $u(x, y)$ and $v(x, y)$ being the displacement field of the pattern [7][8]. Taking into account Eq. (1), DIC reduces to a comparison of subsets belonging to different digital images.

Two different approaches can be adopted:

- The Eulerian approach use the non-deformed state as reference and it results to be accurate for small deformations;
- The Lagrangian approach allows to handle large deformations by using the previous deformed state as reference for the subsequent step. In this case, error accumulation problems during the correlation processes can occur [9].

A 2D-DIC analysis was performed using a 24.1 MPixel SLR camera equipped with a 60 mm macro lens, with a sampling rate of 0.5 Hz. The resultant resolution of the images for all the samples studied is found to be equal to 20 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$. The trigger was controlled by an open source tethering software and the test area was illuminated by led light to ensure a fair level of contrast. The computer aided processing phase was performed using the open source 2D DIC software Ncorr [10]. The correlation was, in particular, carried out using circular subsets having radius equal to 20 pixels, overlapped by 5 pixels, and a Lagrangian approach was selected.

The DIC analysis was carried out during monotonic tensile loading of samples in displacement control at the speed of 2 mm/min.

2.3 Thermoelastic Stress Analysis

Thermoelastic Stress Analysis (TSA) is a full field technique able to retrieve the temperature variation induced by the Thermoelastic Effect [11][12]. Under elastic behaviour and adiabatic conditions, experimentally achieved by applying a cyclic load, the temperature variation at the loading frequency for an orthotropic transversely isotropic material is given by the following relationship [13]:

$$\Delta T = -\frac{T_0}{\rho C_p} (\alpha_L \cdot \Delta \sigma_L + \alpha_Z \cdot \Delta \sigma_Z) = -\frac{T_0}{\rho C_p} \alpha_L \left(\Delta \sigma_L + \frac{\alpha_Z}{\alpha_L} \Delta \sigma_Z \right) \quad (2)$$

where T_0 is the absolute sample temperature, ρ and C_p the homogenised bulk material density and specific heat, α_L and α_Z the coefficients of thermal expansion in the principal material directions, and σ_L and σ_Z the principal material stresses, with subscripts L and Z indicating the longitudinal and transverse out-of plane fibre directions and Δ the amplitude variation. The temperature variation component of Eq. (2) is obtained by filtering a sampled sequence of thermograms over a time window, and performing a Fast Fourier Analysis of the acquired temperature signal, in order to retrieve the amplitude and phase of the harmonic component at the same frequency of the applied load [14]. As stated by the thermoelastic effect law of Eq. (2), this harmonic is proportional to a linear combination of the principal material stresses.

TSA has been recently proposed as a suitable full-field non-contact technique for investigating the through thickness surface of Fibre Reinforced Polymer laminates [15][16], and it offers some unique potentials to directly evaluate stress information of interlaminar stress

fields. In this work a Flir X6540sc infrared thermocamera has been used to acquire thermograms from the through-thickness face of cycling TCT samples. The samples were subject to sinusoidal loads at 3 Hz in a MTS 810 servo-hydraulic testing machine, with a peak to peak load amplitude of 1-9 kN. The IR camera was positioned 40 cm away from the sample, and mounted a 50 mm focal length F/2 lens. This resulted in an instantaneous field of view (Ifov) of about 0.12 mm. The sampled images consisted in a subwindow of the focal plane array, comprising 512×160 pixels. All thermograms were acquired with an integration time of 3186 μ s, and a sampling frequency of 60 Hz, over a time window of 13 secs. During this time the IR camera was fed with a lock-in reference signal having the same frequency of the applied load. This allowed the filtering of the thermoelastic harmonic to be carried out in the Flir software THESA. The same filtering lock-in analysis was also carried out using a Matlab® routine developed by the authors [14], allowing to compare the results with the output from the commercial software.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tests on pre-preg CFRP

This lot of samples was used to investigate the onset of Mode II delamination under monotonic tensile loading, and no full-field experimental stress analysis was performed. It was observed that thin samples (1.5 mm) reached the ultimate tensile stress failure condition before the critical loads for delamination onset. This suggests that there can be a size effect also related with the failure mode. Regarding the thicker samples, it was found that the residual stiffness after the start of crack propagation was similar to the one before initial crack onset. This causes some difficulties in the univocal determination of the critical load from the tensile curve. Figure 2a reports a typical load vs. displacement curve for a TCT specimen where the first nucleation occurs for a load of about 20 kN.

Finally, the expected simultaneous onset of four delamination fronts, as predicted by the theoretical model, was usually not detected. Figure 3 shows the case of two tests on 3 and 4.5 mm thick samples, where the crack onsets are clearly asymmetrical. This behaviour may be induced by a not perfectly symmetrical geometry of the samples, or spurious loads in the loading system. This uncertainties anyway suggest that the TCT configuration might not be sufficiently robust in guaranteeing the conditions for a pure mode II simultaneous multiple onset.

The results of this preliminary experimental campaign inspired a deeper experimental observation of the phenomena.

Figure 2: Load vs. displacement curves of quasi-static tests: a) pre-preg CFRP sample; b) Vacuum bagged CFRP sample.

Figure 3: non-symmetric delamination onset for two samples.

3.2 Tests on vacuum bagged CFRP

DIC analysis was performed after the images acquisition and data were post-processed. In particular, Figure 5 shows the analysis referred to a load of 5 kN that corresponds to the average of the cyclic load applied in the TSA. The image reports the Load Vs. Displacement curve and the maps of strain components ϵ_{zz} , ϵ_{xx} and ϵ_{xz} where z and x indicate the through-the-thickness direction and the fibres direction, respectively. The ϵ_{zz} strain map shows a concentration of deformation in the region close to the crack tips. In particular, a compression zone (dark blue) is surrounded by a tension region.

It is believed that the high compression ϵ_{zz} in the area of the transverse cut is also determined by the more compliant resin pocket enclave, that is formed during manufacturing. It is interesting to observe that on the external uncut plies, i.e. the ligament section, the ϵ_{zz} concentration turns positive. Far from the crack tips, strain levels are much smaller and noisy. Taking into account the strains along the x direction, it is again noticed that the area above the transverse cut is characterized by a high positive ϵ_{xx} . Moving outward from the zone of the cut, the material above and below the cut has smaller tensile ϵ_{xx} values than the lateral areas (the skins), where the load is mainly transferred.

Figure 4: DIC analysis results.

The antisymmetric spectrum that characterizes the shear strain plot is due to the coordinate reference system. Shear strains results to be zero in correspondence of the middle plane. It is important to notice that the strain field around the crack tips presents zz -components that may induce a mode-mixity in the failure mechanism. Moreover, such observed strain field is not symmetric and it is then potentially able to develop asymmetrical crack onset and propagation.

Results of the TSA are summarized in Figs 5-7. In particular, Figure 5 shows full field maps of the amplitude and phase of the harmonic corresponding to the thermoelastic signal. Figure 6 is a close up of Fig 5, centered on the transverse cut fibres area. Figure 7 collects the Fourier power spectrum in the frequency domain of the sampled temperature signal from points R, B, C, whose location is the one indicated by the arrows in Fig. 5a and 6a.

A qualitative evaluation of the thermoelastic signal is here provided commenting the general features of the reported maps, and then focusing on the three selected points locations. In order to allow readers unfamiliar with TSA to better follow the discussion some general features of the thermoelastic signal are here recalled. The thermoelastic signal can be thought as the harmonic at the loading frequency embedded in the more general temperature signal evolution [14]. As such, the thermoelastic signal can be represented as a trigonometric term:

$$S = A \cos(\omega_L \cdot t + \phi) \quad (3)$$

In (3) A is then the amplitude of the thermoelastic effect induced temperature variation, and is given by the absolute value of Eq. (2). In particular, it can be written:

$$A = |\Delta T| \propto |\alpha_L \sigma_L + \alpha_Z \sigma_Z|$$

$$\phi = \begin{cases} \alpha + 0^\circ & \text{if } (\alpha_L \sigma_L + \alpha_Z \sigma_Z) < 0 \\ \alpha + 180^\circ & \text{if } (\alpha_L \sigma_L + \alpha_Z \sigma_Z) > 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The information about the sign of the thermoelastic effect is codified in the phase, where α is a generic angle, comprised between -90° and 90° , which depends on the initial phase shift between the sinusoidal loading signal and the triggering time of temperature sampling. If sampling were synchronized with the loading signal then α would be known, but this is not essential. In fact, any point in the sample can have only two values of ϕ , differing by 180° , according to the sign of $\alpha_L \sigma_L + \alpha_Z \sigma_Z$ in the point.

In the present case Figures 5b and 6b indeed show that all points have only two phase values (two main colors in the phase map), differing by 180° . The lack of phase leakage, i.e. the absence of intermediate phase values, is also a hint that the material achieved adiabatic conditions, which is a requirement for TSA [11]. In order to associate the phase values with a specific sign of the stress function, a point in the zone far from the transverse cut was considered (e.g. point R). For such point the stress field can be considered uniaxial, and A in Eq. 4 depends only on $\alpha_L \sigma_L$. Since σ_L is a positive tensile stress, the sign of the stress function here depends only on α_L . It is well known that the coefficient of thermal expansion in the fibres direction for CFRPs is very small, and could become also negative if the fibres volume fraction is high [13]. On the contrary, α_Z is always positive and may be significantly higher than α_L , up to two orders of magnitude [13]. Two consequences arise: there is an uncertainty on whether the contribution of σ_L is additive or not to the contribution of σ_Z , and secondly the thermoelastic signal in orthotropic CFRP laminas is always much more sensitive to the transverse stress component. From the analysis of the acquired thermograms it was possible to ascertain that in points like R, i.e. in prevalent uniaxial stress, the temperature decreased during the increase of the tensile load. By taking into account the minus sign of Eq. 2, this means that the material under investigation has $\alpha_L > 0$.

The amplitude map in Figure 5a shows that, apart from some localized zones near the transverse cut, the thermoelastic signal is low and does not present any specific pattern. In the remote area, far from the transverse cut, a prevalent uniaxial σ_L stress field is expected, with $\sigma_Z = 0$, which then justifies the low signal (see comments above). Moving nearer to the cut zone, a prevalent shear mode is expected to

progressively take place. Such stress field should theoretically give a null thermoelastic signal, since a pure shear mode is associated to zero values of both σ_L and σ_Z . Therefore, the low thermoelastic signal near the cut, of amplitude and phase similar to the remote areas under uniaxial tension, is an indication that a pure shear mode is probably not fully achieved.

The phase map shown in Fig. 5b is almost uniform anywhere but in the zone above and below the cut, where there is a near 180° shift. This feature of the phase map was observed in all tested samples (three identical samples were prepared and tested), although results shown in this paper refers to one specific specimen of the lot. As stated above, the 180° phase shift is to be associated with a change in the sign of the stress function $\alpha_L\sigma_L + \alpha_Z\sigma_Z$.

Figure 5: Thermoelastic amplitude and phase components from the vacuum bagged TCT sample.

Figure 6: Close up of thermoelastic amplitude and phase components from the transverse cut area of the TCT sample (vacuum bag lot).

In light of the above considerations, the following discussion will focus on the thermoelastic signal measured from the three selected points R, B, C:

Point R

A prevalent uniaxial stress is present here. The lack of contribution from a transvers stress component σ_Z on one side, and the low value of α_L on the other, justify the relatively low amplitude of the

thermoelastic effect induced ΔT . Furthermore it is $\alpha_L > 0$, so the value of the phase of the thermoelastic signal in this point should be associated with a positive value of the stress functional $\alpha_L \sigma_L + \alpha_Z \sigma_Z$.

Point B

The most noteworthy feature here is a change of the phase by 180° . Therefore, the sign of $\alpha_L \sigma_L + \alpha_Z \sigma_Z$ is negative. Since α_L and α_Z are both positive, and do not change their sign over the entire specimen surface (they are material properties), the reason for this phase change is the arising of a negative stress component σ_L and/or σ_Z . It is very unlikely that σ_L is negative. In fact if the cut fibres produce a material discontinuity they are like the flanks of a centered crack, and the boundary condition would require here $\sigma_L = 0$. More likely, there is a resin pocket reestablishing the material continuity between the cut fibres. Here then the stress component is still positive due to the traction load. This is indeed in agreement with the results of the DIC, which show a sharp rise of $\varepsilon_{xx} = \varepsilon_L$ in the cut area. Moreover, the DIC results indicate also that ε_{xx} is positive over the whole sample surface. In conclusions, the most likely reason for the phase change is the arising of a negative σ_Z component. This is once again in agreement with the DIC results indicating a negative ε_{zz} strain component around the cut area. It is here recalled that also in plates with centered cracks the zone above and below the crack flanks is generally in compression.

Point C

It is here observed the presence of a small zone of very high thermoelastic signal, located near the right hand side tip of the cut. The phase in such zone of high signal is the same as in the remote field (e.g. point R). Hence, the stress functional $\alpha_L \sigma_L + \alpha_Z \sigma_Z$ is positive. Therefore, this local stress concentration could be due to either a sharp rise of a traction σ_L stress, or the presence of a traction σ_Z stress. Unfortunately, TSA is not able to resolve which of the two components is effectively present and prevalent. It can be suggested that since $\alpha_L \ll \alpha_Z$, it is unlikely that such a high rise of the thermoelastic signal is produced only by σ_L , so probably there is also a contribution from the transverse component σ_Z . In addition, the DIC analysis indicates the presence of positive transverse deformations ε_{zz} in the skin zones (i.e. the external layers of the transverse cut section). If this were true, it would indicate a situation where a mixed mode loading condition might arise. One final consideration is that this sharp rise of the thermoelastic signal is observed only in C, thus representing a significant asymmetry of the stress field around the transverse cut, which can foster early unilateral delamination onset and a mixed mode loading scenario.

Some final considerations about the TSA can be made based on Fig. 7, which shows the power spectrum of the thermal signal acquired over time from points R, B, C.

Figure 7: Power spectrums in frequency domain obtained with the Matlab FFT function on the temperature sampled from points R, B, C defined in Figs. 5a and 6a.

The power spectrum in the frequency domain is obtained by the Matlab Fast Fourier Transform algorithm. It is seen that for all three points the thermoelastic signal, i.e. the harmonic at 3 Hz, is well above the average noise level. Even for points B and R, which are located in areas with much smaller thermoelastic signal, the thermoelastic component is anyway well detectable. The remaining spectral content does not show any significant rise of power at other frequencies, i.e. all other harmonics are randomly distributed at the same power value, which is an indication that they are random noise

components, and there is no specific energy dissipation term able to rise up.

It is finally reported that all thermoelastic analyses were performed twice. In the first run by means of the commercial post-processing software FLIR THESA, which uses a reference physical signal to perform the lock-in analysis ending up with the filtering of the thermoelastic component. In the second run by using algorithms developed by the authors that perform a Fast Fourier Transform of the sampled temperature and use a self-reference, extracted by the Fourier spectrum, as the lock-in signal [14]. In both cases, the TSA results were perfectly reproduced with the same identical features, adding confidence that the TSA analysis performed in this work is reliable.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work two full field experimental stress analysis techniques have been successfully implemented to investigate the stress and strain field on the through-the-thickness face of Transverse Crack Tension CFRP specimens. Two CFRP materials, one obtained from pre-pregs, and one from a vacuum bagged impregnated dry fabric, have highlighted the difficulty to onset symmetric and simultaneous crack delamination fronts, due to non perfect symmetry of specimen geometry and loading conditions. The implemented experimental techniques have also evidenced different asymmetrical features in the stress and strain components, which likely contribute to determine local delamination onset conditions, and might also favor some degree of mode mixity in crack initiation and propagation.

Further work is in due course to exploit the implemented experimental setups and evaluate alternative geometries inspired by the TCT configuration, but specifically optimized to be more robust against specimens imperfections in developing a pure mode II delamination onset.

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